

NIST on a Chip with Alkali Vapor Cells: Initial Results

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Abstract — We describe progress at NIST to develop a series of “chip-scale”, SI-traceable electromagnetic reference instruments based on microfabricated alkali vapor cells. We anticipate being able to realize the second, the meter, the volt, the ampere and the kelvin using microfabrication techniques and spectroscopic measurement of alkali atom energy levels. We report here on initial fabrication efforts to develop optical wavelength references in which atomic vapor cells are integrated with single-mode photonics.

Index Terms — Atomic clock, chip-scale atomic clock, current, temperature, voltage, wavelength, standard

I. INTRODUCTION

The combination of microfabrication techniques and advanced laser technology has enabled a new generation of compact, low power and potentially low cost “chip-scale” atomic clocks. These instruments demonstrate a power dissipation 30 times lower than any previous atomic clocks and are currently finding growing use in a variety of timing applications that require low power and high stability. However, long-term drifts and environmental sensitivity related to the presence of the buffer gas in the alkali vapor cell results in low accuracy ($\sim 10^{-8}$) without periodic calibration.

Fig. 1. Conceptual illustration of a chip, which realizes one or more SI units on a low-cost, highly manufacturable platform.

Using techniques developed largely for our previous work in this area, we are now developing a number of chip-scale instruments that exhibit intrinsic SI-traceability [1]. These instruments are all based on optical or microwave spectroscopy of alkali atoms confined in microfabricated vapor cells. The SI-traceability is enabled by knowledge of constants such as the speed of light, which is defined, and atomic g-factors, and DC polarizabilities, which have been previously measured to high accuracy with respect to the SI. Fig. 1 shows conceptually the

goal: one or multiple chips that realize some set of SI units in a compact, inexpensive package. We anticipate being able to realize four (new SI) base units (the second, the meter, the kelvin, and the volt) and one additional electrical unit (the ampere) using this method. Such a chip could potentially be manufactured at low cost and integrated into products and systems enabling continuous, SI-traceable calibration.

II. PHOTONICALLY INTEGRATED WAVELENGTH REFERENCES

Optical wavelength references based on optical spectroscopy [2] have been under development for many years and the best references are currently achieving uncertainties below 10^{-17} [3]. In the interest of making small, highly manufacturable wavelength references, we are developing methods for integrating microfabricated alkali vapor cells with single-mode photonics. The basic structure is shown in Fig. 2(a). A SiN photonics chip is fabricated on a silicon substrate by first depositing a SiO layer and the SiN layer. The SiN layer is then lithographically patterned and etched to form a single mode waveguide that runs, for example, from the edge of the chip (where it is pigtailed to single-mode fiber) to the center. At the end of the waveguide, a grating output coupler is patterned, which couples light from the waveguide into a free-space optical mode propagating roughly perpendicular to the chip surface. An optical photograph of the ends of a waveguide and the associated diffractive output coupler is shown in Figure 2(b). The nitride layer is then covered with a second oxide layer. The silicon frame from the microfabricated alkali vapor cell is fusion bonded directly onto the top oxide layer and the resulting

Fig. 2 (a) Schematic of the photonic integrated alkali vapor cell showing the SiN waveguide layer, the diffractive output coupler and the microfabricated vapor cell. (b) A photograph of a SiN waveguide ending in a diffractive output coupler.

cell preform is filled [4] with a source of alkali atoms and bonded under vacuum. A photograph of one of the filled cells is shown in Fig. 3(a). A small pill of a Rb chromate and a Zr-Al reducing agent is placed in one part of the cell before bonding. After bonding, the pill is heated to above 400 °C using a focused high-power laser to react the materials and create pure alkali metal in the cell. The evolved Rb is shown, along with the remnants of the pill on the left side of Fig. 3(a). On the right side, the waveguides can be seen.

Fig. 3 (a) Photograph of complete photonic integrated alkali vapor cell showing the reacted Rb chromate pill and Rb metal on the left and the photonic waveguides on the right. (b) Absorption spectroscopy of atoms in the cell from light sent through the diffractive coupler (red) and reference cell (blue).

We then coupled light at 795 nm from the edge of the chip, through the waveguide that ran under the cell frame and out of the diffractive coupler. The absorption was measured at a cell temperature of approximately 90 °C as a function of laser frequency as it was scanned near the Rb D1 line. The Doppler-broadened absorption spectrum is shown in Fig. 3(b), along with a larger reference cell. The absorption spectrum remained visible and unchanged when measured two months after initial fabrication indicating that if small leaks are present, they are small enough to avoid oxidizing the alkali atoms over this time period. We have measured the optical frequency of the peak centers in the absorption spectrum in Fig. 3(b) with respect to the reference cell and find they are the same within 10 MHz, indicating that the residual gas in the cell is less than about 1 Torr and consistent with zero.

Transit time broadening is a critical mechanism that will limit the resolution of the wavelength reference as a function of the

optical mode field diameter and is particularly important for wavelength references based on the small optical modes typical of photonic structures. The transit time broadening is given in terms of the atom velocity, v , and mode field diameter, L , as $\Delta\nu_{TT} \approx 0.9 v/L$. For Rb atoms with typical thermal velocities near 300 m/s a mode field diameter larger than about 100 μm is required to obtain a transit-time linewidth below 3 MHz.

VI. CONCLUSION

These results demonstrate a form of on-chip optical spectroscopy, which has been demonstrated in other groups [5-7] over the last few years. One important way in which our work differs from previous work is that the coupling from waveguide to a free space optical mode allows for larger mode volumes and reduced transit time broadening. By designing larger output couplers, for example, we anticipate being able to generate field mode diameters as large as 100 μm , suitable for observing Doppler-free lines in alkali vapors.

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